

Vision-Language Pretraining for Variable-shot Image Classification

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Abstract. Contrastively pretrained vision-language models (VLMs) such as CLIP have shown impressive zero-shot classification performance without any classification-specific training. They create a common embedding space by contrastively pretraining an image and a text encoder to align positive image-text pairs and repel negative pairs. Then zero-shot classification of an image can be performed by measuring the cosine similarities between the image embedding and embeddings of texts that describe the classes. However, relevant works do not address the scenario in which few image examples for some (not all) classes are available. In this novel task which we term variable-shot classification (v-shot), these models fail due to the embedding space modality gap, i.e. the fact that image-to-image similarities are higher than image-to-text ones. To this end, we propose to enable v-shot capabilities in pre-trained VLMs with minimal training complexity by re-projecting embeddings of frozen pre-trained image encoders using a shallow network, RectNet, which we train both with the standard CLIP contrastive loss function, as well as a novel modality alignment loss function specifically constructed to bridge the modality gap. Finally, we introduce three v-shot classification benchmarks, on which the proposed architecture achieves 32.22%, 29.58% and 45.15% increases in top-1 classification accuracy respectively.

Keywords: variable-shot classification · v-shot classification · vision-language pretraining · computer vision.

1 Introduction

The rise of joint image-text contrastive pretraining has transformed how computers understand the link between visual content and language. Models like CLIP [21] utilize large web-collected image-text datasets to achieve impressive zero-shot classification abilities, excelling in tasks like image captioning and retrieval without fine-tuning. Moreover, with minor adaptations, they can perform tasks

such as open-vocabulary object detection [30, 16, 15, 13] and open-vocabulary image semantic segmentation [11, 28, 27]. In all tasks, zero-shot classification (image, object or pixel classification) is achieved by comparing visual embeddings with embeddings of text descriptions of the classes.

However, there can be classification scenarios where purely textual descriptions are insufficient for certain fine-grained classes, whether due to the ambiguity of language or due to the need for excessively long descriptions to sufficiently define the class. In such cases, combining textual descriptions for some classes with a few image examples for others (few-shot) could be beneficial. We propose this new paradigm, termed "v-shot classification", in order to benchmark classification generalizability. In this setting, query image embeddings are compared to the text embeddings for some classes and the image embeddings for others.

Nevertheless, a recently studied phenomenon called the embedding space *modality gap* [12, 26, 25, 23] causes image and text embeddings to occupy distinct clusters within the latent space, leading to higher intra-modality similarities (image-to-image) compared to inter-modality similarities (image-text). Consequently, when using existing contrastively pretrained image/text encoders, test images are overwhelmingly classified into image-based classes, ignoring text-based ones, making v-shot classification infeasible.

To enable v-shot classification in pretrained CLIP models while retaining their strong zero-shot capabilities, we propose to better align image embeddings with the text embeddings of zero-shot classes with minimal training complexity and inference overhead using RectNet, a 2-layer embedding rectification MLP network placed after a frozen pretrained CLIP image encoder. Additionally, we propose a Contrastive Modality Alignment loss (\mathcal{L}_{CMA}) to bridge the modality gap by pushing same-modality embeddings apart and bringing positive image-text pairs closer, complementing the baseline CLIP contrastive loss. Finally, we introduce a set of v-shot classification datasets and experimentally demonstrate that RectNet achieves state-of-the-art v-shot classification performance. Although \mathcal{L}_{CMA} helps bridge the gap, the best v-shot classification results are achieved by RectNet trained only on the baseline CLIP contrastive loss. In summary,

- We propose "v-shot classification", a novel classification setting with classes of mixed zero and few image availability, as well as set of benchmarks based on common image classification datasets.
- To enable v-shot classification capabilities in pre-trained VLM architectures, we introduce a shallow neural network, RectNet, that projects pretrained image embeddings to the text embedding space with trivial computational overhead and significant training efficiency.
- We propose a novel contrastive loss function to reduce the modality gap that causes CLIP to fail in v-shot scenarios.
- We show that RectNet achieves the best top-1 and top-5 v-shot classification accuracy across all datasets.

2 Related Work

Our proposed strategy is a VLM pretraining scheme to minimize the modality gap and enable v-shot classification in VLMs. Therefore, the related work in this section is categorized into methods that do contrastive VLM pretraining and methods that study the modality gap phenomenon.

Contrastive VLM pretraining Contrastive language-image pre-training has gained popularity since the introduction of CLIP [21] and ALIGN [7], which applied contrastive learning [2, 8] to large-scale image-text datasets. Both models excel in zero-shot transfer tasks, including classification and retrieval. Following their success, there has been a surge of research in contrastive VLP. DeCLIP [10], SLIP [17] and MaskCLIP [5] reinforce the baseline CLIP training with per-modality self supervision to achieve superior performance, with SimSiam [3], SimCLR [2] or masked image modeling [1] for self-supervision of the visual encoder, and Masked Language modeling [4] for the text encoder. CyCLIP [6] added geometric consistency regularizations to the CLIP objective. SigLIP [29] substituted the softmax loss with a sigmoid loss, allowing for efficient training with much larger batch sizes, while simultaneously enhancing classification performance at smaller batch sizes. However none of the above methods evaluate their performance on the v-shot classification task. We show that due to the modality gap in CLIP-based methods, v-shot classification cannot be accomplished.

CLIP modality gap Methods like CLIP bring positive image-text pairs close in the embedding space while pushing negative pairs apart. However, a noticeable "modality gap" exists between the embedding distribution means of the two modalities (see fig. 2a), a phenomenon highlighted by several works [12, 19, 26, 25, 23, 22]. Liang et al. [12] first introduced this phenomenon, attributing it to factors like the narrow cone effect, different parameter initializations for two different encoders (image/text), the nature of the contrastive loss itself, non-linear activation functions, the value of the softmax temperature, and mismatched image-text pairs in pretraining datasets. Interestingly, they demonstrate that increasing the modality gap can sometimes improve specific downstream tasks like zero-shot classification. Udandarao [26] found that the spread of image embeddings influences the gap, showing that as the mean distance between image embeddings decreases, the text embeddings yielding the lowest contrastive loss are further away from their respective image embeddings. Shi et al. [25] demonstrated that the contrastive loss comprises conflicting uniformity and alignment terms, trapping CLIP in a local minimum with a pronounced modality gap. Oh et al. [19] reiterated that high uniformity and alignment are essential for quality embeddings. They blend images with corresponding text to create hard negative samples, incentivizing further alignment and minimizing the gap. Schrodi et al. [23] showed that only a few embedding dimensions form the gap, which arises

from the information imbalance between modalities: images provide detailed appearance information, while texts offer sparse descriptions. More detailed captions reduce the gap. In contrast to all these works, we study the effect of the gap on the v-shot classification task.

Fig. 1: The v-shot classification scheme (VSC). In fig. 1a a query image embedding is compared to text embeddings of class descriptions (standard zero-shot classification). In fig. 1b a query image embedding is compared to text embeddings of class descriptions for some classes and to RectNet image exemplar embeddings for other classes (VSC).

3 Proposed Method

In this section, we first review the contrastive vision-language pretraining strategy. We then formulate the novel v-shot classification scenario and lastly, we introduce RectNet, our image embedding re-projection network, as well as our novel gap-closing loss. Refer to Fig. 1 for the outline of the proposed classification setting with RectNet.

3.1 VLM contrastive pretraining

Vision-language pretraining involves a large dataset $\mathcal{D}_{pre} = (I_i, t_i) | i = 1, \dots, r$ of r image-caption pairs, where I_i is an image and t_i a corresponding text prompt. The goal is to create a common representation space where cosine similarities reflect semantic similarity between these different modalities. This space can be

realised using two encoding functions:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_i^v &= E^v(I_i), \\ \mathbf{e}_i^t &= E^t(t_i), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where E^t, E^v are usually represented by deep neural networks.

The common multi-modal embedding space is achieved by jointly training the two modality-specific encoders on a contrastive loss function [21]:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CLIP}} = -\frac{1}{2B} \left(\sum_i \log \frac{\exp(\mathbf{e}_i^v \cdot \mathbf{e}_i^t / \tau)}{\sum_j \exp(\mathbf{e}_i^v \cdot \mathbf{e}_j^t / \tau)} + \sum_i \log \frac{\exp(\mathbf{e}_i^v \cdot \mathbf{e}_i^t / \tau)}{\sum_j \exp(\mathbf{e}_i^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_j^v / \tau)} \right), \quad (2)$$

where τ is the softmax temperature parameter, B the batch size and \cdot the dot product.

3.2 V-shot Classification (VSC)

In the zero-shot image classification task, each class c is represented by the embedding \mathbf{e}_c^t of some text t_c that describe this class, e.g. "*an image of a {class}*". An image I_i can be then classified by assigning to it a class c_i using the following:

$$c_i = \arg \max_c (\mathbf{e}_i^v \cdot \mathbf{e}_c^t), \quad (3)$$

where the embeddings come from encoders that are pretrained on the contrastive objective.

In cases where a subset of the class set contains classes with no sufficient textual description available, the classification task is modified in order to incorporate k example images I_c^i , $i = 1, \dots, k$ for such object classes (image-described classes) instead of text descriptions. In that case, which we term Variable-shot Classification (VSC), the classification task can be summarised in the following formulation:

$$\begin{aligned} c_i &= \arg \max_c (\mathbf{e}_i^v \cdot \mathbf{e}_c), \\ \text{where } \mathbf{e}_c &= \begin{cases} E^t(t_c), & \text{for text-described classes} \\ \frac{1}{k} \sum_i^k E^v(I_c^i), & \text{for image-described classes} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Visualization of CLIP embeddings from image-text pairs (Fig. 2a) of CC3M [24] shows distinct clusters for each modality. This separation makes vanilla CLIP embeddings unsuitable for VSC, as input image embeddings \mathbf{e}_i^v are more similar to other image embeddings than to any text embedding, regardless of the true class. Consequently, images are assigned to classes represented by example images, neglecting textually described classes.

Fig. 2: t-SNE visualisation of embeddings of 10 random image-text pairs from the CC3m [24] dataset using: i) vanilla CLIP (figure 2a), and ii) our RectNet+ \mathcal{L}_{CMA} (figure 2b). Different shapes indicate different modalities and colours represent correspondences. Clearly, RectNet is able to eliminate the two-cluster structure while keeping positive image-text pairs close together.

3.3 Embedding Rectification Network (RectNet)

Retraining VLM encoders for VSC requires substantial GPU resources and energy, and might degrade zero-shot classification due to limited training data. Instead, we propose RectNet, a shallow neural network that aligns modalities by re-projecting pretrained CLIP image embeddings into the text embedding space. This allows us to keep the VLM image encoder frozen and only optimize RectNet weights, ensuring efficiency.

Given the strength of pretrained CLIP encoders in vision-language reasoning, RectNet is placed directly after the CLIP image encoder:

$$\mathbf{e}_c = \begin{cases} E^t(t_c), & \text{for text-described classes} \\ \frac{1}{k} \sum_i^k R(E^v(I_c)), & \text{for image-described classes,} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $R(\cdot)$ denotes RectNet. Both CLIP encoders remain frozen during training, optimizing only the RectNet parameters. A visualization of RectNet is shown in Fig. 3.

3.4 Contrastive modality alignment loss

For successful v-shot classification, positive image-text pairs must exhibit higher similarities than both negative image-text pairs and negative image-image pairs (when comparing a query image with an image exemplar). To achieve this within a CLIP-style classification framework, we propose to introduce same-modality negatives in the contrastive objective, creating the following contrastive modality alignment (CMA) loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}_{CMA} = -\frac{1}{2B} \left(\sum_i \log \frac{\exp(\mathbf{e}_i^v \cdot \mathbf{e}_i^t / \tau)}{\sum_{j \neq i} \exp(\mathbf{e}_i^v \cdot \mathbf{e}_j^v / \tau)} + \sum_i \log \frac{\exp(\mathbf{e}_i^v \cdot \mathbf{e}_i^t / \tau)}{\sum_{j \neq i} \exp(\mathbf{e}_i^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_j^t / \tau)} \right). \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3: RectNet architecture and training. Fig. 3a shows where RectNet is placed in the CLIP framework as well as its training scheme. Fig. 3b shows a detailed overview of RectNet architecture and parameters.

In order to maintain the powerful zero-shot classification capability and at the same time align the two modality-specific clusters, the final loss function is updated as:

$$\mathcal{L}_f = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{\text{CLIP}} + \beta \mathcal{L}_{\text{CMA}}, \tag{7}$$

where α and β are weighting coefficients, both set to 1.

4 Experiments

4.1 Experimental Setup

RectNet pre-training RectNet comprises two blocks, each with a linear and a batch normalization layer, a hidden space of 2048, and a ReLU activation function after the first layer (see Fig. 3b). We train RectNet on top of a frozen pre-trained CLIP ViTB/32 image encoder on the proposed loss function (eq. 7) using Adam optimizer with a batch size of 2048 on the CC3M dataset [24], with 2,334,451 image-text pairs available. The weights are initialized with the identity matrix to leverage the robust baseline CLIP weights. Training for 30 epochs took less than 7 hours on a single NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU.

VSC Datasets To empirically validate the VSC capability of RectNet, we conduct extensive evaluations on custom classification tasks combining a general-purpose image classification dataset for the zero-shot classes with a dataset containing specialised (fine-grained) classes as the few-shot classes, as text descriptions of fine-grained classes are generally inadequate. We create three such classification benchmarks, by combining CIFAR100 [9] (containing 100 general-purpose classes, such as "shark", "telephone", "lobster", etc.) and each of the following fine-grained image classification datasets:

- FGVC-Aircraft [14], which is a dataset that contains photos of aircraft, categorized into aircraft models.
- Oxford-IIIT Pet [20], which contains photos of pets, classified into dog/cat breeds, and
- Flowers102 [18], which contains flower species commonly occurring in the United Kingdom.

4.2 Performance on VSC datasets

For all three tasks, we compare the baseline CLIP classification performance with RectNet pretrained on the baseline CLIP loss (RectNet-ft) and RectNet trained on the proposed loss (eq. 7). In the rest of the section, zero-shot and v-shot performance on the VSC benchmarks is analyzed and finally, the relationship between the modality gap and VSC performance is discussed.

Zero-shot classification We first evaluate on the baseline zero-shot classification, where all classes are text-described (eq. 3). These evaluations can be seen in Tables 2, 1 and 3 in the blocks titled "zero-shot". While it is evident that the baseline CLIP model still has the top zero-shot classification accuracy figures, this metric is only presented for the sake of completeness and is not the main focus of this work.

V-shot classification VSC is evaluated on pretrained VLM encoders by comparing a query image embedding with text description embeddings for regular classes (CIFAR) and image exemplar embeddings for fine-grained classes (FGVCAircraft, OxfordPets and Flowers102). Due to non-alignment between the two modalities in the baseline CLIP embedding space, as described in the previous section, the baseline pretrained CLIP encoders present a 0.0% accuracy in zero-shot classes, as it can be observed in Tables 2, 1 and 3. Note that we create different variants of classifier image embeddings, each time using a different number (k) of image exemplars for each few-shot class (see eq. 5). It can be also observed that, in general, accuracy rises in proportion to k .

By incorporating RectNet into the CLIP VSC scheme, VSC becomes feasible even with just one image exemplar per class (see rows labeled 'v-shot: k=1' in Tables 2, 1 and 3). Although for OxfordPets the zero-shot performance of vanilla CLIP cannot be surpassed with v-shot (Table 1), probably due to the high availability of pet photographs in the CLIP pretraining dataset, with just five example images for the fine-grained classes of the other two datasets (Tables 2, 3) the zero-shot performance can be surpassed. Using all available image exemplars from each fine-grained dataset's training set, all v-shot experiments have shown that RectNet outperforms the baseline. The following accuracy gains can be observed for each dataset compared to CLIP's zero-shot performance:

- CIFAR+FGVC-Aircraft: a 6.55% and 6.92% increases can be observed for overall top-1 and top-5 accuracy respectively, while a 13.1% and 13.61% increase is observed in top-1 and top-5 accuracy for the fine-grained classes.

Table 1: Zero-shot and V-shot classification performance on CIFAR100 + OxfordPets. "zs" and "fs" means zero-shot and few-shot respectively. Best results are highlighted with **bold**, while second best are underlined.

	Model	Overall		zs classes		fs classes	
		top1	top5	top1	top5	top1	top5
zero-shot	CLIP	70.42	90.91	64.31	88.01	86.95	98.76
	RectNet-ft	62.55	88.40	60.52	85.41	68.03	96.48
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	39.97	57.69	52.95	74.66	4.88	11.82
v-shot: k=1	CLIP	9.09	18.92	0	0	<u>33.64</u>	<u>70.06</u>
	RectNet-ft	55.45	<u>82.21</u>	65.17	89.22	29.19	63.26
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>53.59</u>	82.28	<u>60.10</u>	<u>84.98</u>	35.98	75.00
v-shot: k=5	CLIP	16.69	25.40	0	0	61.79	94.04
	RectNet-ft	61.45	88.90	65.17	89.22	51.41	88.02
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>58.66</u>	<u>84.11</u>	<u>58.39</u>	<u>80.51</u>	<u>59.39</u>	<u>93.85</u>
v-shot: k=10	CLIP	18.68	25.96	0	0	69.17	<u>96.11</u>
	RectNet-ft	63.56	90.05	65.17	89.22	59.21	92.29
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>60.88</u>	<u>84.83</u>	<u>58.54</u>	<u>80.36</u>	<u>67.23</u>	96.93
v-shot: k=20	CLIP	20.15	26.31	0	0	74.61	<u>97.44</u>
	RectNet-ft	64.92	90.64	65.17	89.22	64.26	94.47
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>62.59</u>	<u>85.03</u>	<u>58.83</u>	<u>80.22</u>	<u>72.74</u>	98.04
v-shot: k=50	CLIP	20.92	26.39	0	0	77.45	<u>97.71</u>
	RectNet-ft	65.79	90.84	65.17	89.22	67.45	95.21
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>63.97</u>	<u>85.43</u>	<u>59.38</u>	<u>80.53</u>	<u>76.37</u>	98.65
v-shot: k=100	CLIP	21.54	26.49	0	0	79.76	<u>98.09</u>
	RectNet-ft	66.69	90.93	65.17	89.22	70.80	95.55
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>64.77</u>	<u>85.24</u>	<u>59.31</u>	<u>80.18</u>	<u>79.54</u>	98.91

Table 2: Zero-shot and V-shot classification performance on CIFAR100 + FGV-CAircraft. "zs" and "fs" means zero-shot and few-shot respectively. Best results are highlighted with **bold**, while second best are underlined.

	Model	Overall		zs classes		fs classes	
		top1	top5	top1	top5	top1	top5
zero-shot	CLIP	42.02	69.91	65.05	88.97	18.99	50.84
	RectNet-ft	38.99	64.93	61.38	86.20	16.62	43.66
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	29.25	47.31	52.95	74.65	5.30	19.97
v-shot: k=1	CLIP	7.81	19.04	0	0	15.63	<u>38.10</u>
	RectNet-ft	40.07	63.85	65.15	89.20	<u>15.00</u>	38.50
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>38.74</u>	<u>62.16</u>	<u>63.04</u>	<u>87.04</u>	14.43	37.28
v-shot: k=5	CLIP	12.60	27.34	0	0	25.20	54.68
	RectNet-ft	44.19	70.88	65.14	89.20	<u>23.24</u>	<u>52.55</u>
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>42.57</u>	<u>68.57</u>	<u>63.21</u>	<u>86.46</u>	21.93	50.68
v-shot: k=10	CLIP	14.17	29.60	0	0	28.34	59.20
	RectNet-ft	45.57	73.05	65.14	89.20	<u>25.99</u>	<u>56.90</u>
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>43.96</u>	<u>70.71</u>	<u>63.58</u>	<u>86.70</u>	24.35	54.73
v-shot: k=20	CLIP	15.52	31.41	0	0	31.05	62.81
	RectNet-ft	46.84	74.73	65.15	89.20	<u>28.53</u>	<u>60.26</u>
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	45.17	72.29	63.76	86.75	26.58	57.83
v-shot: k=33	CLIP	17.35	33.48	0	0	34.70	66.96
	RectNet-ft	48.57	76.83	65.15	89.20	<u>32.00</u>	<u>64.45</u>
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>47.40</u>	<u>74.56</u>	<u>63.90</u>	<u>86.86</u>	30.89	62.25

Table 3: Zero-shot and V-shot classification performance on CIFAR100 + Flowers102. "zs" and "fs" means zero-shot and few-shot respectively. Best results are highlighted with **bold**, while second best are underlined.

	Model	Overall		zs classes		fs classes	
		top1	top5	top1	top5	top1	top5
zero-shot	CLIP	65.95	87.40	63.82	87.97	67.94	86.86
	RectNet-ft	57.65	83.83	60.18	84.68	55.29	83.04
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	30.16	52.25	52.23	73.93	9.61	32.06
v-shot: k=1	CLIP	30.62	43.02	0	0	59.51	83.25
	RectNet-ft	60.87	85.42	64.91	89.04	57.11	<u>82.04</u>
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>58.65</u>	<u>81.91</u>	<u>59.02</u>	<u>82.72</u>	58.30	81.16
v-shot: k=5	CLIP	41.06	47.41	0	0	83.55	96.28
	RectNet-ft	70.01	91.57	64.91	89.04	74.76	<u>93.93</u>
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>68.37</u>	<u>86.76</u>	<u>58.83</u>	<u>81.35</u>	<u>77.25</u>	91.79
v-shot: k=10	CLIP	44.11	48.48	0	0	89.71	98.43
	RectNet-ft	73.69	92.79	64.92	89.04	81.86	<u>96.27</u>
	RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	<u>71.77</u>	<u>87.64</u>	<u>59.46</u>	<u>81.21</u>	<u>83.24</u>	93.63

(a) KDE of intra and inter modality similarities for the baseline CLIP. (b) KDE of intra and inter modality similarities for RectNet-ft. (c) KDE of intra and inter modality similarities for RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f .

Fig. 4: Kernel density estimation (KDE) visualization of similarities between positive and negative image-text pairs, as well as intra-modal similarities. The held-out validation set of CC3m is used.

- CIFAR+Flowers102: a 7.74% and 5.39% increases can be observed for overall top-1 and top-5 accuracy respectively, while a 13.92% and 9.41% increase is observed in top-1 and top-5 accuracy for the fine-grained classes.
- CIFAR+Oxford-IIIT Pet: Both the overall and fine-grained classes' top-1 and top-5 accuracies are slightly reduced, probably due to the strength of the text embeddings of classes that relate to pets, as they are prominent in the pre-training dataset. However, accuracy on CIFAR classes is still higher than the baseline.

It must be noted that VSC with RectNet does not require any further training on classification datasets than its pre-training on the CLIP loss (eq. 2) or the proposed loss (eq. 7). Moreover, the exemplar embeddings can be computed in a pre-testing phase and saved, therefore during the testing v-shot classification stage, no overhead is induced to the baseline CLIP model.

Table 4: Size of the modality gap (as per [12]), evaluated on CC3m. The lower the size, the more aligned the two modalities are.

Model	Modality gap
CLIP	0.8237
RectNet-ft	0.8540
RectNet- \mathcal{L}_f	0.1553

Modality gap size and performance We evaluated the modality gap for each method as proposed in [12] using the held-out evaluation set of CC3M. The results, shown in Table 4, reveal an interesting trend: while we expected VSC performance to improve as the gap decreased, the opposite occurred. Although \mathcal{L}_f reduces the modality gap and achieves better VSC accuracies than the baseline CLIP model, RectNet trained only on the regular CLIP loss function (eq. 2) yields the best overall results despite increasing the gap. This suggests a more complex relationship between the gap and VSC performance. As illustrated in Fig. 4, \mathcal{L}_f (subfig. 4c) enhances positive image-text pair similarities over intra-image similarities. Conversely, RectNet-ft (subfig. 4b) does not make positive inter-modal similarities stronger than intra-image similarities. However, compared to the baseline CLIP (subfig. 4a), RectNet-ft brings the peaks of the probability density functions for inter-modal and intra-image similarities closer together, which may explain its VSC accuracy gains over the baseline CLIP.

4.3 Influence of embedding dimensions in VSC performance

As noted in [23], only a handful of embedding dimensions form the modality gap. We evaluate VSC performance on the CIFAR100+Flowers102 dataset by gradually removing the most influential embedding dimensions (dimensions with the highest absolute difference between the mean image embedding and the mean text embedding, following [23]) of baseline CLIP image and text embeddings. The results are shown in Table 5. It can be seen that in v-shot settings, by removing the most influential dimension the performance in image-described classes drops significantly, while performance in text-described classes increase sharply (therefore enabling VSC capability), although not reaching the zero-shot performance levels of the full 512 dimensions. Then, with each removed dimension the performance on all classes is diminishing, but gradually coming up again after removing 4 dimensions. Here, k is the number of image examples for the few-shot classes.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the proposed approach introduces variable shot (v-shot) image classification, a novel classification setting for vision-language models, along with a comprehensive set of v-shot evaluation benchmarks. Through our experiments, it was demonstrated that CLIP struggles with v-shot classification due to the

Table 5: V-shot classification performance on CIFAR100+Flowers102 with progressive removal of gap-forming dimensions of baseline CLIP embeddings.

	Model		Overall		CIFAR100		Flowers102	
	emb. dim	top1	top5	top1	top5	top1	top5	
zero-shot	512	65.95	87.40	63.82	87.97	67.94	86.86	
	511	59.38	83.06	55.87	79.28	62.65	86.57	
	510	56.94	77.87	48.82	70.96	64.51	84.31	
	509	49.58	70.05	36.28	56.83	61.96	82.35	
	508	49.88	70.44	36.91	57.23	61.96	82.75	
	507	52.88	73.41	42.19	63.48	62.84	82.65	
v-shot: k=1	512	30.62	43.02	0	0	59.15	83.09	
	511	48.85	74.49	42.45	67.49	54.81	81.01	
	510	35.74	56.75	15.41	30.76	54.67	80.95	
	509	29.22	44.44	2.08	5.30	54.51	80.89	
	508	29.52	45.11	2.57	6.58	54.63	81.00	
	507	30.13	46.46	3.90	9.47	54.56	80.91	
v-shot: k=5	512	43.35	49.82	0	0	83.72	96.23	
	511	61.93	82.85	46.71	70.41	76.11	94.44	
	510	49.18	65.85	20.44	35.21	75.95	94.38	
	509	40.83	52.24	3.31	7.02	75.78	94.36	
	508	41.26	53.05	4.12	8.69	75.85	94.36	
	507	42.13	54.92	6.05	12.61	75.73	94.33	
v-shot: k=10	512	46.50	50.86	0	0	89.80	98.24	
	511	66.79	84.68	47.97	71.38	84.31	97.06	
	510	54.13	67.85	22.03	36.49	84.02	97.06	
	509	45.32	53.95	3.78	7.67	84.02	97.06	
	508	45.77	54.77	4.69	9.36	84.02	97.06	
	507	46.77	56.83	6.88	13.63	83.92	97.06	

modality gap between visual and textual representations. To tackle this issue, we proposed a novel contrastive modality alignment loss, which is specifically designed to reduce this gap. This loss function was used to train our image embedding re-projection network, RectNet. RectNet rectifies the pretrained CLIP image embeddings, retaining the strong zero-shot capabilities of pretrained CLIP models while significantly reducing the modality gap. This enables efficient adaptation of pretrained VLMs for v-shot classification. Our results showed a marked improvement in v-shot classification accuracy across all proposed datasets. As next steps, we plan to extend our research to address the v-shot object detection problem. Additionally, we aim to further explore the structure of the modality gap and its impact on v-shot performance, which may provide deeper insights and lead to further advancements in vision-language model capabilities.

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